

Guideline for Annotating Dentofacial Markers to Distinguish Real and Synthetic Faces

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Supplementary material to the article:
**Dentofacial Markers for the Detection of Faces Generated
by Diffusion-Based Text-to-Image Artificial Intelligence
Models**

Introduction

The generation of images using artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly common across various domains and user needs. However, despite significant advances in realism, AI-generated images often exhibit subtle anatomical inaccuracies that distinguish them from real human portraits. This guideline provides a structured framework for identifying and annotating key dentofacial features that can help determine whether a facial image is real or synthetic.

Annotations are focusing on specific dentofacial attributes. Each feature is defined with clear operational criteria, along with conditions for excluding the attribute (when it is not visible or applicable). This guide supports consistent and reproducible annotation by trained evaluators.

Dentofacial Markers

The following attributes are used for annotation:

1. Physiological shape of the teeth
2. Natural teeth color
3. Natural number of teeth
4. Anatomically correct gum
5. Correct light reflection in the eyes
6. Physiological shape of the eyelashes

7. Consistency in the eye gaze direction
8. Symmetry in pupil and iris
9. Round pupil shape
10. Presence of visible pores
11. Physiological shape of the outer ear
12. Physiological shape of the nose

1 Physiological Shape of the Teeth

This attribute refers to the natural anatomy of teeth, including the proper alignment, contours, and differentiation of tooth types (incisors, canines, premolars, molars) as normally observed in a human dentition.

Operational Definition

Teeth must appear anatomically plausible in shape and position within the oral cavity, taking into account the differentiation between front and back teeth as well as the natural curvature and spacing.

Not applicable when

The subject's mouth is closed, rendering the teeth completely or mostly invisible.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

2 Natural Tooth Color

Refers to the natural coloring of human teeth, generally ranging from white to yellowish tones, without exaggerated or artificial hues.

Operational Definition

Tooth color should fall within the accepted VITA shade guide (e.g., A1–D4). Acceptable variations include natural tints in white, off-white, or light yellow. Bright, saturated, metallic, or neon-colored teeth are considered unrealistic.

Not applicable when

The subject's mouth is closed or the teeth are not adequately visible due to image angle, lighting, or occlusion.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

3 Natural number of teeth

This attribute evaluates whether the number of visible teeth corresponds to the expected dentition based on the extent of the subject's smile.

Operational Definition

The number of visible teeth should be anatomically plausible given the smile type:

Full smile Both upper and lower dental arches are visible, typically including central incisors, lateral incisors, canines, and premolars.

Medium smile Only the upper dental arch is visible, showing teeth from central incisors to premolars.

Low smile Primarily upper front teeth are visible, generally limited to incisors and canines.

A significantly lower or higher number of teeth than typically expected should be annotated as negative.

Not applicable when

The subject's mouth is fully closed or the smile is not visible enough to determine the number or type of exposed teeth.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

4 Anatomically correct gums

This attribute assesses whether the gums exhibit natural anatomical shape and coloration, focusing on their appearance, position, and integration with surrounding oral structures.

Operational Definition

The gums should appear pale to medium pink in color (depending on individual variation) and have a knife-edge appearance at the gingival margin, framing each tooth clearly. The gumline should:

- Terminate cleanly without visibly merging into the teeth or lips.
- Follow the natural curve around each tooth, particularly the upper front teeth.
- Be free from unnatural color artifacts (e.g., greens, purples) or anatomical distortions.

Blurring, uneven edges, or an unrealistic transition between gums and teeth should be annotated as negative.

Not applicable when

The subject's mouth is fully closed or the gums is obscured due to angle, lighting, or occlusion.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

5 Correct light reflection in the eyes

This attribute evaluates the presence and placement of light reflections (specular highlights) within the eyes, which simulate the effect of ambient lighting on the moist surface of a real human eye.

Operational Definition

The eyes should display small, bright specular highlights (typically white or very light-colored) on the cornea, reflecting the direction of ambient light. Reflections should be:

- Located on both eyes, in symmetrical or consistent positions depending on the light source.
- Appropriately sized—neither overly exaggerated nor missing entirely.
- Physically plausible in shape (e.g., circular or slightly elongated depending on the light source).

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable, as annotations are only performed when both eyes are open and visible.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

6 Physiological shape of the eyelashes

This attribute assesses whether the eyelashes exhibit natural anatomical characteristics, including realistic curvature, density, positioning, and separation from surrounding skin structures.

Operational Definition

Eyelashes should be:

- Present on both the upper and lower eyelids of both eyes.

- Emanating from the correct anatomical position (the eyelid margin) with no unnatural merging into the skin or eyeball.
- Properly curved, typically upward on the upper eyelid and downward or straight along the lower eyelid.
- Moderate in density, within a realistic range (e.g., approximately 75–80 lashes on the lower eyelid and 90–160 on the upper eyelid; although not individually countable, excessive clumping or unnaturally sparse patterns should be annotated as negative).
- Free from artifacts such as floating lashes, fused clumps, or non-parallel orientations that break natural patterns.

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable, because both eyes should be visible.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

7 Consistency in the eye gaze direction

This attribute evaluates whether both eyes are aligned in a consistent and anatomically plausible direction, indicating that the subject is focusing on the same target or area.

Operational Definition

Both pupils should appear to be oriented toward a common point of focus, rather than diverging or pointing in unrelated directions. Specifically:

- The angle of orientation between the pupils should demonstrate natural convergence or parallel alignment consistent with typical gaze behavior.
- The horizontal and vertical alignment (height and spacing) of the pupils should be symmetrical, without noticeable discrepancies.
- The gaze should not appear cross-eyed (converging too sharply), wall-eyed (excessively diverging), or misaligned vertically.

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable, as gaze direction can be assessed as long as both eyes are visible.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

8 Symmetry in pupil and iris

This attribute assesses whether the pupils and irises of both eyes are symmetrical in size, shape, and vertical alignment, contributing to a natural and balanced appearance.

Operational Definition

The pupils and irises should meet the following criteria:

- Both pupils should be vertically aligned and located at the same height relative to the eyelids.

- The diameters of the pupils should be approximately equal, without significant size variation.
- The irises in both eyes should appear circular and uniform in shape and color, with similar size and positioning.

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

9 Round pupil shape

This attribute evaluates whether the pupils appear anatomically correct in shape, specifically round and consistent across both eyes.

Operational Definition

Each pupil should be:

- Clearly visible and circular in shape under normal lighting and eye position.
- Symmetrical between both eyes, with no significant variation in contour.
- Free from distortions such as elliptical, oval, teardrop, or irregular shapes, which can suggest generation artifacts.

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

10 Presence of visible pores

This attribute assesses the presence of natural skin texture, particularly pores, which are typically visible on areas of higher sebaceous activity such as the cheeks, nose, and forehead.

Operational Definition

The skin should display fine, evenly distributed texture, including small visible pores, especially in the following regions:

- Cheeks (particularly the area beside the nose)
- Nose bridge and tip
- Central forehead

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

11 Physiological shape of the outer ear

This attribute evaluates whether the outer ear exhibits a realistic anatomical structure, including identifiable folds, contours, and proper spatial positioning.

Operational Definition

The ear should display:

- A recognizable ear lobe (attached or free-hanging), with full or partial visibility.

- Natural folds and contours, such as the helix, antihelix, concha, and tragus, if visible.
- Proper spatial positioning on the side of the head, typically aligning between the level of the eyes and the tip of the nose in height.

Not applicable when

This attribute is not applicable when both ears are entirely obscured by hair or head coverings.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

12 Physiological shape of the nose

This attribute assesses whether the nose demonstrates a realistic anatomical form, including clear definition of the nasal bridge, nasal tip, and nasal wings, with accurate nostril structure.

Operational Definition

A physiologically accurate nose should exhibit:

- Two well-defined nostrils, clearly separated and symmetrical.
- Nasal alae that are distinct and anatomically placed, not merged or collapsed into surrounding structures.
- A visible and consistent nasal bridge, forming a continuous structure from the glabella (between the eyes) to the tip of the nose.
- Natural width, orientation, and proportion consistent with varied human anatomy.

Not applicable when

This attribute is always applicable.

Positive Examples

Negative Examples

